

Communicating about communication: Using graph comics to explore communication networks in letters of Early Romanticism

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“When visualizing data, the only certifiable fact is that it's impossible to avoid interpretation.” This statement by D'Iganzio and Klein (2020, 80) shows the crux of every visualisation. On the one hand it facilitates communication about the insight into data we get through our research: We can share this “simply” by showing it. On the other hand, by doing so we are not communicating crucial information the observer needs to understand this visualisation: Information about the context of the data or biases in the database. In the case of a network visualisation, we might encounter the infamous “hairball”, indicating a dense network with so many actors and relationships, its readability has been lost in their overwhelming entanglements. In addition, we might also want to share more information about the temporal changes in the network or to show parallel changes that are important for the context of our research question. These research questions have a crucial role because from the beginning of the analytic process, they shape the data, from which we build our networks, as well as the results and interpretations we draw from them. In fact, in this process, we are showing a specific representation of the data shaped by our research focus which we furthermore hope is interpreted in the way we intend it to be. So how can we enrich our visualisations with more information? How can an *observer* of a visualisation become the *reader* of it?

An attempt to solve this problem is the use of graph comics (Bach et al. 2016). Graph comics serve as a tool for data-driven storytelling and help to improve the communication of what exactly is shown in a network visualisation. They show how the network was built from which data points, from which relationships it is formed and how these can be interpreted, how its structure and appearance can be interpreted and read, and much more (cf. use cases on graph comics website⁶ and fig. 1). Hence the users have the opportunity to *read* the comic and follow a narrative instead of just looking at a visualisation. In their test with a focus group, Bach et al. encountered first that “comics are a flexible and expressive medium, enabling communication with a variety of visuals and text”. Second, graph comics help “to express changes in networks” because “they are readable by a wider audience and applicable to a variety of usage scenarios” (Bach et al 2016, 3679).

In our talk we want to share our experiences with graph comics, demonstrate how they may serve as a form of internal as well as external documentation, and furthermore help to transport more information about forms of communication in the network of letters of Early Romanticism. Our research is embedded in the DFG-project "Correspondences of Early Romanticism. Edition - Annotation - Network Research" (<https://briefe-der-romantik.de>). The Early Romanticism in Jena and Berlin is considered the outstanding intellectual revolution of young German authors and scholars at the turn of the epoch around 1800. The group operated publicly and sustainably, dispersively yet network-forming; they reflected and practised "Geselligkeit," for example, through the communication form of letters. The analysis of these epistolary communication processes among the Early Romantics is one of the major desiderata of Romanticism research, which we intend to address. The project aims to build up a database that consists of the letters exchanged among the key protagonists of Early Romanticism (such as Friedrich, Dorothea, August

⁶ <https://aviz.fr/~bbach/graphcomics/>

Wilhelm, and Caroline Schlegel, Novalis, among others) and their correspondents between 1790 and 1802, covering various 'prehistories' up to the dissolution of the Jena Circle (Schanze 2018, 18). By analysing the communication networks, we intend to highlight important actors (or, thinking in graph comics, main characters) in these communication processes, identify potential clusters, search for signs of loss or (re-) establishment of contact as well as set all these factors in a temporal and comparative context. Ultimately, through these results we intend to get a better understanding of knowledge transfer and production in the Romantic circle.

At this stage of the project, however, the database is not yet completed. At the time of writing, around 3,300 of a projected 6,500 letters have been published on the project website in varying states of annotation. This brings its own set of challenges in interpreting and understanding the networks created, and communicating these biases efficiently. At the same time, the project is still developing a network methodology to analyse these processes of communication and network transfer, which is then intended to be applied to the final data set – meaning, a clear and concise way of documenting the successes and dead-ends, the potentials and pitfalls of different methods is needed that can be understood intuitively not only by Digital Humanists but also by literary scholars which are less familiar with formal methods and quantitative thinking – as they make up parts of the project team as well as the intended audience. For these reasons, the project will experiment

with the use of graph comics to facilitate understanding the dynamics and temporal changes in communication based on the networks of the early romantic correspondences.

Additionally, we are also aiming at improving science communication in our project: Considering the large database as well as the many actors involved, just showing the visualisation of the network (e.g. sender-receiver-network) might result in one of the earlier mentioned “hairballs” and not communicate anything of the results apart from the fact that we used a network to analyse the data. As it is impossible to visualise data without interpretation, through the comics more context or framing can be given by reducing the visualisation to abstract symbols or drawings and then contextualising them by using comic strips – all the while never losing the explanatory power inherent in the visual approach. Furthermore, graph novels could also be used to explain the bias or uncertainties in the data so that readers of the comics have this already in mind.

In the presentation, we aim to give an overview of this experimental integration of graph comics in our documentation processes, while in doing so, presenting the first results of our work on the communicative network of the Early Romanticists.

References

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DFG-Project “Correspondences of Early Romanticism: Editing – Annotating – Network Research”:
<https://briefe-der-romantik.de>

Graph Comics: <https://aviz.fr/~bbach/graphcomics/>